

Graphite Fiber Composite Retaining Rings for Large Generators

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ABSTRACT

A novel fabrication method, Bias Ply Winding, has been demonstrated for the manufacture of graphite fiber retaining rings for large turbine generators. Results of a material selection and fabrication process study, as well as test data on full section rings will be presented.

The function of retaining rings are to restrain and keep from moving in a radial direction the copper conductors on the rotors of central power station generators. Retaining rings used on existing generators are forgings of cold worked austenitic steel with a yield strength of 180 ksi.

The graphite fiber composite retaining rings evaluated were 32 inches in diameter and 2.25 inches in wall thickness, weighing 180 pounds. The bias ply winding method to be described, involved the winding of pre-oriented fiber prepreg under controlled tension. High pressure cure resulted in a highly densified, uniform structure. Mechanical, thermal and nondestructive test data on the full thickness rings will be presented.

The composite rings were spin tested at cyclic speeds to 6,600 rpm at 80°C, simulating a 40 year service life. Spin testing was found to have no effect on the structural integrity of the rings as determined by ultrasonic and mechanical testing.

Fracture mechanics testing and analysis of the construction and materials selected showed, that unlike steel, it was not possible to fail the composite rings by radial crack propagation.

Figure 5 — Fiber composite retaining ring in position for ultrasonic testing using C-scan equipment.